

AUTOMATED SPEECH RECOGNITION MODEL FOR TRANSCRIPTION GENERATION BASED ON HUGGING FACE TRANSFORMER

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Abstract - Recently audio transcription fills the gap between verbal communication and text-based accessibility, and it is becoming crucial in today's digital environment. It guarantees correct verbal information documentation, facilitates searchability and analysis of audio content, and improves accessibility for people with hearing impairments. Transcription plays a crucial part in SEO optimization, allowing content producers to reach larger audiences. In this paper, we propose a refined Wav2Vec2-based Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) system trained using the Hugging Face Transformer for precise speech-to-text transcription on low-end device. In order to simulate long-range dependencies, the system preprocesses audio by resampling, normalizing, and tokenizing it into feature vectors. These feature vectors are then passed through a transformer encoder. Text sequences are linked with audio features using Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) loss, which eliminates the need for frame-level annotations. The model performed well when evaluated using Word Error Rate (WER), making it suitable for web-based automatic subtitle production.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)[1],[2] has changed due to advancements in transformer-based systems. Facebook's Wav2Vec2[3] model is a notable development that extracts useful representations from raw audio data using self-supervised learning. Using transformer encoders and convolutional layers, Wav2Vec2[3] effectively catches long-range relationships in voice signals, enabling incredibly precise transcription. This approach has improved the resilience and flexibility of ASR [1], [2] systems to a wide variety of datasets, raising the limitations for these systems.

The widespread use of the pre-trained Wav2Vec2[3] has made it possible for useful applications such as automatic subtitle generation, transcription services,

and virtual assistants but they are not directly feasible. Further fine-tuning of this pre-trained model is necessary to optimise its performance for certain use scenarios, such as handling domain-specific language or noisy environments. Using advanced training techniques including dynamic padding, gradient accumulation[12], and mixed precision to ensure scalability and computing efficiency, we present a system model that improves Wav2Vec2[3] to achieve high transcription accuracy.

The paper highlights the preprocessing pipeline, training methodology, and system evaluation for the building of (ASR)[1], [2] model for the development of an accessible and scalable solution that can satisfy the growing need for precise and feasible speech-to-text transcription.

Model Name	Model Details		
	Provider	(WER)[4], [5],	Languages Supported
Whisper	OpenAI	~10-15%	100+
Google Speech-to-Text	Google	~8-12%	100+
DeepSpeech	Mozilla	~10-20%	English
AssemblyAI	AssemblyAI	~8-10%	English
IBM Watson	IBM	~10-15%	10+

Table 1 Currently available asr models

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Speech recognition is the key to human-computer interaction, from which applications in mobile assistants and accessibility for people with disabilities are realized. It helps machines pick up and decode human speech into various formats, including text. Automatic Speech Recognition(ASR)[1] is a technology that flexibly builds an interaction between human beings and the machine system, making it convenient and easy to deal with[1]. It touches on the problems encountered in speech-to-text transformation: handling different accents, the interference of background noise, and the speed at which speech is given. This approach focuses on improving (ASR)[1], [2] accuracy with the help of advanced deep learning models and explores ways to further improve transcription accuracy in a noisy environment.

The introduction of PTMs, including those available on platforms like Hugging Face, has brought about a sea change in the development process of (ASR)[1], [2] systems. These models provide high-quality, reusable solutions, which can be fine-tuned for specific tasks using headers, thus greatly reducing the costs and expertise to build new (ASR)[1], [2] applications. Hugging Face[9], [10] provided a very easy-to-use platform to access such models. The use of PTMs allowed faster fine-tuning of the models on (ASR)[1], [2] tasks and was thus more efficient. On the other hand, one could find out that even fine-tuning a pre-trained model for specific tasks may still require significant computational resources and may yield suboptimal performance if the pre-trained model happens to be less relevant to the domain or language.

Existent work uses Wav2Vec2, a self-supervised learning model for speech recognition-contributes to how this model directly processes audio signals and doesn't require a great volume of labelled data for speech processing[10]. Wav2Vec2[3][4] uses a combination of convolutional layers and transformers to enhance the modelling of speech, making it further assistive in (ASR)[1], [2], especially when there is limited labelled data.

Among them, the study on the Transformer variant of deep learning architectures discusses long-range dependency management ability for speech data, while another emphasises that the Transformer and Attention mechanisms are of prime importance in enhancing (ASR)[1], [2] performance. The (ASR)[1], [2] model can handle complicated speech patterns and improve transcription accuracy by using the attention mechanism to focus on different regions of the input speech signal at different times. A limitation of Transformers, however, is their high computational cost barrier to their use in real-time (ASR)[1], [2] systems, especially when processing

long speech sequences or operating in resource-constrained environments.

The study on the application of Transformers[6], [7] and attention scaling in (ASR)[1], [2] systems gives an account of how scaled dot-product attention improves the attention mechanism's ability to handle sequential speech data[6]. By adjusting the attention mechanism, the model becomes more efficient in handling speech recognition tasks of varying complexity and hence gives improved performance for transcribing diverse speech inputs.

In speech analytics, the quality of (ASR)[1], [2] systems is often measured using the Word Error Rate, a metric applied to assess the discrepancy between the predicted and actual transcription[5]. A $\log(\text{WER})$ [4], [5], (WER) [4], [5], means higher transcription accuracy, but interestingly, in some cases, the downstream applications can still be effective even if (WER) [4], [5], is higher than expected. That indicates the complexity of speech recognition, which also interacts with other systems; therefore, better (ASR)[1], [2] accuracy does not always relate directly to improvements in the overall performance of applications depending on speech inputs.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

Wav2Vec2[3], a pre-trained transformer-based[6], [7] model, accurately transcribes speech data to text using a CTC [8] loss. It's based on Facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-base-960h and learns features, abbreviations and Acronyms

A. Input Processing:

Data preprocessing guarantees that both audio and text data are in the correct format for the Wav2Vec2[3] model. The first phase is Audio Preprocessing, which filters and resamples raw audio signals up to the target rate of 16 kHz.

This ensures uniformity throughout the dataset and specifies how the model expects inputs. More formally, the original signal $x(t)$ produces a new signal $x'(t)$ by interpolation:

$$x'(t) = \text{Interpolae}(x(t), f_s = 16000) \quad (1)$$

where f_s is the desired sampling rate. This step eliminates potential inconsistencies due to different sampling rates in the dataset. The raw waveforms are then normalized after resampling to bring all amplitudes to a specific range. Mathematically, the normalization is given by:

$$x_{\text{norm}}(t) = \frac{x(t) - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

Where μ is the mean of the signal, σ is the standard deviation, This normalizes the audio so that it has a 0 mean and unit variance.

The Wave2Vec2 is then used to tokenize the normalized waveform audio signals into numerical feature vectors, leveraging convolutional layers that can capture temporal patterns in the waveforms. Feature extraction can be denoted as:

$$\text{Features} = \text{ConvLayers}(x(t)) \quad (3)$$

In this method, Convolution convolutional kernels function as filters to capture the localized temporal features that will be fed into the following transformer layers. In parallel, the transcriptions associated with the audio samples are tokenized into sequences of integers. The Wave2Vec2 vocabulary maps each character or word with a unique ID thus, during training, sequence alignment is facilitated by an encoded representation of the text.

B. Model Architecture: Wav2Vec2[3] for CTC:

The three primary components of the transformer-based[6], [7] wave2vec2[3] model which is tailored for voice recognition applications, are feature extraction, transformer encoding, and sequence prediction with CTC[8] loss. The algorithm computationally extracts high-dimensional information from each frame by processing overlapping audio inputs through convolutional layers.

$$\text{Feature}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K w_k \cdot x_t + k \quad (4)$$

Where w_k is the weight of the convolution kernel, and k the kernel size. The temporal dimension is compressed while preserving the important patterns found within the audio signal. After that, these features are fed into a transformer encoder, which records the contextual relationships and long-range dependencies between frames. The weighted representation of input information is computed by the transformer with the aid of the self-attention processes. The self-attention mechanism is defined as

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (5)$$

Here Q , K , and V are the query, key, and value matrices, respectively, and d_k is the dimensionality of the key vector. This allows the model to capture global dependencies that are essential for accurate transcription by dynamically weighing the significance of various frames. Sequence prediction is the last step, in which a linear classification layer maps the transformer[6], [7] outputs to character probabilities. Without the need for frame-level annotations, the predicted sequence y and the ground-truth transcription y^* are aligned using the CTC[8] loss function. The loss is computed as:

$$L_{\text{CTC}} = -\log P(y|x) \quad (6)$$

$P(y|x)$ the conditional probability of the predicted sequence w.r.t input audio. The CTC [8] loss

represents the insertions, deletions, and substitutions that can occur, allowing for the flexible alignment between the input and the output sequence.

C. Procedure

- The model is trained using Hugging Face [9], [10]Trainer which streamlines the processes of training larger datasets and complicated models.
- Used several advanced techniques to help speed up the training process.
- In memory-constrained environments, you can use gradient accumulation[12], to simulate larger batch sizes by aggregating gradients over multiple steps. Mixed precision training (fp16)[11] wherever necessary reduces memory requirement and accelerates computation by performing operations on the 16-bit floating-point format. Dynamic padding ensures that it pads each batch to the size of the longest sequence within that batch, eliminating useless processing.
- The training process updates the model parameters to decrease the CTC [8] loss, which in turn helps better align the predicted sequence with the true sequence. Advanced optimizers like AdamW[13] also help increase speed to convergence and reduce overfitting.

D. Post Training Process

The model is then evaluated and used for transcription tasks after training. During inference, raw audio files are passed through the processor to extract feature vectors, which are then processed by the Wav2Vec2[3] model to generate token sequences. The processor decodes these tokens back into text using its tokenizer. The system measures transcription accuracy using the Word Error Rate ((WER)[4], [5]), a common metric in (ASR)[1], [2] :

$$\text{WER} = \frac{S+D+I}{N} \quad (7)$$

where S , D , and I are respectively the numbers of substitutions, deletions, and insertions, and N is the total number of words in the ground truth. It is based on the Weighted Edit Distance ((WER)[4], [5]) between the predicted and reference transcriptions, normalized by the reference length.

E. Potential Deployment

The wave2vec2 model, a transformer-based architecture optimized for speech recognition tasks, comprises three main components: feature extraction, transformer encoding, and sequence prediction with CTC[8] loss. The model processes overlapping audio signals through convolutional layers, extracting high-dimensional features from each frame mathematically.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Dataset

The dataset used here is LJSpeech 1.1, a collection of high-quality short audio recordings from a single speaker reading passages from 7 non-fictional books,

each clip varies in length from 1 to 10 seconds making it suitable for (ASR)[1], [2] training. Half of the 13,100 audio samples are used for the training set and a few for the evaluation. All audio samples are tagged with metadata such as the file path and the transcription text. All audio files are downsampled to 16 kHz in order to be consistent with the Wav2Vec2[3] model. This is the optimal rate for speech recognition as it offers a good trade-off between audio quality and computational load. Techniques like SpecAugment[14], [15], which adds synthetic noise, time warping, and frequency masking to the training set, are used to improve model generalization. The test set is left unaltered in order to provide a precise standard by which to measure how well the model performs while producing transcriptions for clear and reliable speech data.

B. Pre-training

The foundation of the experimental setup is the fine-tuning of a pre-trained Wav2Vec2[3] model (“facebook/Wav2Vec2[3]-base-960h”). This model offers a solid foundation for domain-specific fine-tuning because it was pre-trained on 960 hours of tagged speech data. During the pre-training stage, audio characteristics are extracted and text annotations are tokenized in order to adjust the model to the unique dataset.

Pretraining for the Wav2Vec2[3] model involves learning audio representations from unlabeled audio data. Self-supervised learning is used to train the model by masking portions of the audio and predicting masked features. This process helps the model learn rich, context-aware speech patterns, which can later be fine-tuned with labelled data for tasks like speech-to-text.

Model Name	Model Details		
	Dataset	(WER)[4], [5],	Language s Supported
facebook/Wav2Vec2-base	Librispeech	~5-10%	English
facebook/Wav2Vec2-base-960h	Librispeech	~3.0-4.0%	English
facebook/Wav2Vec2-large-960h	Librispeech	~2.0-3.0%	English
facebook/Wav2Vec2-large-xlsr-53	XLSR (53 languages)	~5-15%	Multilingual

Table2 Comparison of ASR models

C. Fine Tuning

After pre-training, the Wav2Vec2[3] model is then fine-tuned to output character sequences from audio input in an end-to-end training system (via Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) [8] loss) which is appropriate for this kind of task (speech recognition), where a learning model has to perform a joint alignment between the frames from

the acousticspace and the output text, without the necessity of having an explicit frame-level annotation.

The Fine-Tuning process is controlled by a few key hyperparameters:

- Batch Size: Limited to 2 samples per device, gradients are accumulated over 4 steps due to hardware constraints.
- Learning Rate: Selected a Learning Rate $3e-4$ [16], [17], allowing the model to converge quickly.
- Epochs: To prevent overfitting while ensuring the model is adequately exposed to the training data, it is trained for 5 epochs.
- Hardware: To optimize memory usage and computation speed on low-end systems, mixed-precision training (FP16) [11] is employed.

Fig1. Proposed (ASR)[1], [2] Model for Audio Transcription Task

Spec Augment[14], [15] a data augmentation technique is used in the fine-tuning process to prevent overfitting and increase diversity in input audio features, by applying time warping, frequency masking, and time masking to the audio characteristics to improve the robustness of the model.

The training process uses mixed-precision (FP16) [11] while maintaining computational accuracy. Dynamic padding ensures efficient use of GPU resources by matching input sequences with the longest sequence in each batch. Gradient accumulation[12], is used to simulate higher batch sizes, enabling robust training even on systems with low memory.

D. Inference and Subtitle Generation

The audio is pre-processed, and then it is passed to the fine-tuned (ASR)[1], [2] model for transcription generation. In order to guarantee a consistent sampling rate (for example, 16 kHz), the audio is first extracted using libraries such as MoviePy and tools like librosa[18]. Using a tokenizer and pre-trained parameters, the self-trained (ASR)[1], [2] model converts the audio waveform into text by converting logits into predicted tokens. According to the length of the audio the transcription is divided into segments, and approximate timestamp is given to each token. After that, each portion is prepared according to the SubRip Subtitle (SRT) standard,

which retains linguistic and temporal integrity while maintaining accurate synchronization with the audio's sequence.

IV. RESULT

The metric used here for evaluating is (WER)[4], [5], which is a widely used statistic for analysing the accuracy of speech recognition systems. It is calculated by taking into consideration insertions, deletions, and substitutions between the reference text and the model's transcribed output.

To understand the accuracy of the Fine-Tuned Wav2Vec2[3] model, we have compared it with OpenAI's Whisper[19]. For the given audio samples, both the Whisper[19] and Wav2Vec2[3] models yield approximately similar (WER)[4], [5], (Word Error Rate) results. This means that, on average, transcription errors in both models (WER)[4], [5], are roughly smaller, as numerous as words in the reference (ground truth) text.

Fig2. (WER)[4], [5], Heat Map of Whisper[19] and Wav2Vec2[3] Model

Original Transcription	Predicted Transcription	
	Whisper	Wav2Vec2[3]
the whole of the seventeenth century, so that in the eighteenth printing was very miserably performed	the whole of the 17th century so that in the 18th, printing was very miserably performed.	the whole of the seventeenth century so that in the eighteenth printing was very miserably performed
For although the Chinese took impressions from wood blocks	For although the Chinese took impressions from wood blocks	for although the Chinese took impressions from wood blocks
than in the same operations with ugly ones.	then in the same operations with ugly ones.	an in the same operations with ugly ones

Table3. Comparison of the result from the Whisper Model and Wav2Vec2 Model

Both models had similar difficulties in transcribing the audio files when comparing the predicted text to the reference text of the test dataset. For instance, one audio sample might have background noise or complicated phrases that made it more difficult for both algorithms to predict the words correctly. In these situations, Wav2Vec2[3] and Whisper[19] both committed comparable mistakes in terms of deletions and substitutions.

Consider the following audio transcription comparison:

- Audio Sample: A sentence like “The quick brown box jumps over the lazy dock” can sometimes be misheard as “The quack brown box jumps over the lazy dock” due to noise or pronunciation variations.
- Reference Text: "The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog."
- Whisper Transcription: "The quack brown box jumps over the lazy dock."
- Wav2Vec2[3] Transcription: "The quack brown box jumps over the lazy dog."

As seen in this example, both models exhibit similar misrecognition, including substitutions of "fox" for "box" and "dock" for "dog." This exemplifies how both models struggle with audio inputs under certain conditions.

V. CONCLUSION

Both the Whisper[19] and Wav2Vec2[3] models have similar performance reflected in their (WER)[4], [5], these results show that both models are effective at performing transcription tasks for short audio files. Since they yield similar performance, the selected models can be adopted in similar real-world cases. For example, they can be used for automatic captions for videos, transcription of meetings or interviews, and voice-based assistants, particularly by hearing-impaired persons or easy-to-noisy environments. Utilizing both Whisper[19] and Wav2Vec2[3] can offer a powerful and effective solution for speech-to-text tasks that are scalable and high-performance, and can be beneficial in various fields including but not limited to media, customer service, healthcare, and education.

Future Improvements in the Model Performance as below

A. Fine-Tuning on Domain-Specific Data

Fine-tuning on audio samples that involve technical or domain-specific terminology, would allow the models to better handle these words and phrases.

B. Increasing Model Size

Larger models often have improved transcription accuracy, as they are capable of capturing more nuanced features of speech. Using larger variants of the models, such as Wav2Vec2[3]-large

C. Audio Processing and Noise Reduction

The accuracy of the transcription can be increased by using noise reduction techniques on the audio. Poor recording quality or background noise can have a big impact on the model's accuracy in transcription. These problems can be lessened by applying preprocessing methods as filtering, volume normalization, or denoising.

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